

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15429407

Prevalence Of Contraceptive Utilization And Pregnancy Experiences Among Women Of Reproductive Age: A Pre-Intervention Survey In Ekiti State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Contraceptive utilization remains a crucial strategy for reducing unintended pregnancies and improving maternal and child health outcomes globally. This pre-intervention survey assessed the prevalence of contraceptive use and pregnancy experiences among 99 women of reproductive age in selected Local Government Areas of Ekiti State, Nigeria. Using a descriptive cross-sectional design and interviewer-administered questionnaires, socio-demographic characteristics, contraceptive knowledge, and pregnancy histories were collected. Results indicated that only 36.4% of respondents utilized contraceptives prior to intervention, with oral pills being the predominant method (91.4%). The majority of women were aged 30–39 years (62.6%) and married (56.6%), with 41.4% having attained tertiary education. Despite moderate knowledge levels, cultural and religious barriers limited contraceptive uptake. Pregnancy experiences revealed high fertility patterns, with an average of 3.1 pregnancies per woman and 28.2% reporting five or more pregnancies. History of miscarriage and stillbirth were reported by 23.5% and 9.1% of respondents, respectively. While antenatal care attendance was high (89.9%), early ANC initiation was low (12.1% in the first trimester), and 42.4% of women delivered outside health facilities. These findings align with the Health Belief Model, highlighting perceived barriers as critical impediments to contraceptive use. The study underscores the need for culturally sensitive, community-based reproductive health education to enhance uptake and improve maternal health outcomes in Ekiti State.

Keywords: Contraceptive utilization, Pregnancy experiences, Women, Reproductive Age

INTRODUCTION

Contraceptive utilization plays a critical role in reducing unintended, improving maternal and child health outcomes, and empowering women to make informed reproductive choices (Abah et al., 2024; Abubakar, 2024). Globally, contraceptive prevalence varies widely, with low uptake notably persistent in many low- and middle-income countries, including Nigeria (Guttmacher Institute, 2022; Ameyaw et al., 2021).

Despite efforts to increase awareness and access to family planning services, the contraceptive prevalence rate in Nigeria remains low, with considerable disparities across regions and socio-demographic groups (Akinwale et al., 2020; Abubakar & Abubakar, 2024).

In Ekiti State, like many other parts of Nigeria, socio-demographic factors such as maternal education, age, marital status, economic status, and cultural beliefs significantly influence contraceptive use (Ibikunle et al., 2023; Gbenga-Epebinu et al., 2020; Durowade et al., 2017). Studies have shown that women with higher education levels tend to have better knowledge and higher utilization of contraceptives, whereas younger and less educated women face multiple barriers including misinformation, fear of side effects, and limited access (Abdulrazaq et al., 2014; Adebowale et al., 2021). Cultural and religious norms often shape perceptions and acceptance of contraception, further complicating efforts to increase uptake in rural and semi-urban communities (Akamike et al., 2020; Agunbiade & Osezua, 2018).

Given these multifaceted challenges, community-based reproductive health education programs have been identified as effective strategies to improve contraceptive knowledge and utilization (Kumar et al., 2024; Akamike et al., 2019). However, successful intervention design requires a thorough understanding of baseline contraceptive prevalence and the socio-demographic factors influencing use within the target population. This study presents a pre-intervention survey aimed at assessing contraceptive utilization and its determinants among women of reproductive age in Ekiti State, Nigeria, to provide an evidence base for tailoring effective family planning interventions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Contraceptive utilization is influenced by a complex interplay of socio-demographic factors that vary across contexts. Maternal education consistently emerges as a key determinant, with higher educational attainment linked to increased contraceptive knowledge and use (Abdulrazaq et al., 2014; Ibikunle et al., 2023). Education enhances women's capacity to make informed reproductive choices and navigate healthcare services, reducing unmet contraceptive needs (Adebayo et al., 2021; Gbenga-Epebinu et al., 2020).

Age and marital status also significantly affect contraceptive uptake. Women in their mid-reproductive years (25–34) are more likely to use contraceptives compared to adolescents and younger women, who face stigma and limited access (Durowade et al., 2017; Akamike et al., 2020). Married women generally have higher utilization rates, reflecting family planning's role in birth spacing and household decision-making (Abah et al., 2024; Agunbiade & Osezua, 2018).

Socioeconomic status remains a critical factor; women from higher income groups are more likely to access and use contraceptive services (Abubakar, 2024; Adebowale et al., 2021). Conversely, poverty and limited healthcare infrastructure restrict availability and uptake, especially in rural areas (Durowade et al., 2017; Gbenga-Epebinu et al., 2020). Cultural and religious beliefs heavily influence contraceptive behavior, often perpetuating misconceptions and resistance to modern methods (Akamike et al., 2020; Agunbiade & Osezua, 2018). Misinformation and fear of side effects remain significant barriers, underscoring the need for culturally sensitive education and community engagement (Abdulrazaq et al., 2014; Kumar et al., 2024).

Theoretical Framework

This study is guided by the **Health Belief Model (HBM)**, which posits that individuals' health behaviors, including contraceptive use, are influenced by their perceptions of susceptibility to adverse outcomes, perceived benefits and barriers to taking action, self-efficacy, and cues to action (Katatsky, 1977; Montano & Kasprzyk, 2002). For example, women who perceive high susceptibility to unintended pregnancy and believe in the effectiveness and safety of contraceptives are more likely to use them, provided barriers such as cultural opposition and lack of access are addressed.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study utilized a descriptive cross-sectional design as a **pre-intervention survey** to examine socio-demographic determinants of contraceptive utilization among women of reproductive age in selected Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Ekiti State, Nigeria. The pre-intervention data provide a baseline for measuring the effectiveness of an upcoming community-based reproductive health education program.

Study Setting and Population

Data were collected from **three intervention LGAs** in Ekiti State. Within each LGA, **two markets** were purposively selected, making a total of six markets serving as key data collection sites. A total of 99 **respondents**—women aged 15–49 years—were interviewed across these markets. Similarly, **three control LGAs** with comparable socio-demographic characteristics but no planned interventions were selected, with data collection occurring in two markets per LGA (six markets in total).

Sampling and Sample Size

A total of 99 women of reproductive age were purposively sampled across the intervention markets to gather preliminary baseline information on contraceptive use and associated socio-demographic factors. The relatively small sample reflects the pre-intervention exploratory nature of the study.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire adapted from validated tools, covering socio-demographic characteristics, Prevalence of Contraceptive Utilization and Pregnancy experience. Female data collectors proficient in local languages conducted face-to-face interviews within the markets to facilitate trust and accurate data capture.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was granted by the Adeleke University, Ethics Research Committee and Ekiti State Ministry of Health Ethical Review Committee. All participants provided informed consent after being briefed on the study's objectives, voluntary participation, and confidentiality. Respondent anonymity was rigorously maintained.

Data Analysis

Data were entered into SPSS version 25 for analysis. Descriptive statistics summarized respondents' characteristics and contraceptive use prevalence. Given the exploratory nature of this pre-intervention phase and the small sample size, analysis focused on descriptive trends and preliminary associations. Data from control LGAs will serve as a comparative baseline in the post-intervention evaluation phase.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings from the pre-intervention survey assessing socio-demographic characteristics, contraceptive knowledge, utilization, perceptions, attitudes, barriers, and willingness to uptake contraceptive services among women of reproductive age in selected LGAs of Ekiti State. The findings are interpreted in relation to existing literature to highlight implications for reproductive health interventions.

Sociodemographic Information

Table 1 presents the sociodemographic characteristics of the 99 respondents. The majority of respondents (62, 62.6%) were aged between 30-39 years, followed by 24 (24.2%) respondents aged 20-29 years, and 13 (13.1%) within the age range of 40-49 years.

Regarding marital status, more than half of the respondents (56, 56.6%) were married, while 30 (30.3%) were single and 13 (13.1%) separated. The educational status showed that most respondents had attained tertiary education (41, 41.4%), followed by secondary education (22, 22.2%), primary education (19, 19.2%), and no formal education (17, 17.2%).

In terms of religion, a majority of respondents practiced Christianity (59, 59.6%), while the remaining 40 (40.4%) identified as Muslims. Slightly more than half of the respondents (51, 51.5%) resided in urban or semi-urban areas, while 48 (48.5%) lived in rural communities. Household income data indicated that most respondents (54, 54.5%) earned above 90,000 Naira monthly, with 45 (45.5%) earning between 50,001 and 90,000 Naira. Regarding housing type, a significant majority (73, 73.7%) lived in rented

apartments, whereas 26 (26.3%) owned their homes. On number of living children, most respondents had between one and three children, with 32 (32.3%) having two children, 27 (27.3%) having three children, and 11 (11.1%) having one child. Those with four or more children accounted for 29 (29.3%) of the respondents.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of Respondents (n = 99)

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent (%)
Markets	Okesha	11	11.11
	Ereketa	6	6.06
	Ereja	13	13.13
	Alele	6	6.06
	Okekere	11	11.11
	Oke Oja	8	8.08
	Oja Ogbontitun	6	6.06
	Oja Oba	14	14.14
	Oja mesi	6	6.06
	Oja Ariyasi	6	6.06
	Oja Agbada	6	6.06
	Irewolede	6	6.06
	Age	20-29 years	24
30-39 years		62	62.63
40-49 years		13	13.13
Marital status	Single	30	30.30
	Married	56	56.57
	Separated	13	13.13
Educational status	No formal	17	17.17
	Primary	19	19.19
	Secondary	22	22.22
	Tertiary	41	41.41
Religion	Christianity	59	59.60
	Islam	40	40.40
Place of residence	Rural	48	48.48
	Urban/Semiurban	51	51.52
Monthly income (N)	50,001-90,000	45	45.45
	Above 90,000	54	54.55
Type of housing	Own home	26	26.26
	Rented apartment	73	73.74
Number of children	1	11	11.11
	2	32	32.32
	3	27	27.27
	4 and above	29	29.29

Source: Researcher's field Report, 2025

Table 2 presents the prevalence of contraceptive utilization among the intervention group prior to the intervention which was 63.6%. Out of the 99 respondents, 36 (36.4%) reported using contraceptives, while the majority, 63 (63.6%), were not utilizing any contraceptive method.

Among the contraceptive users (n=36), the intrauterine contraceptive device (IUCD) was used by 6 respondents, representing 17.1% of users. Pills were the most commonly used contraceptive method, with 32 users accounting for 91.4% of contraceptive users. Implants were used by 4 respondents, making up 11.4% of contraceptive users. These findings highlight that before any intervention, just over one-third of respondents utilized contraceptives, with a strong preference for pills over IUCDs and implants.

Table 4.2: Prevalence of Contraceptive Utilization Among Study Groups (Pre-intervention, Intervention Group, n = 99)

	Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent (%)
1	Contraceptive utilization	Utilized	36	36.4
		Not utilized	63	63.6
2	IUCD use	Yes	6	17.1*
		No	29	82.9*
3	Pills use	Yes	32	91.4*
		No	3	8.6*
4	Implants use	Yes	4	11.4*
		No	31	88.6*

Figure 4. 1: Overall prevalence of contraceptive utilization

Table 4 show the Pregnancy Experiences Among Women of Reproductive Age. The study involved 99 women of reproductive age with a mean age of 28.6 years (SD ± 5.4). The majority of respondents, 85 (85.9%), reported having been pregnant at least once, while 14 (14.1%) had never been pregnant.

Among those who had been pregnant (n=85), the average number of pregnancies was 3.1 (SD ± 1.6). Breakdown of pregnancy counts showed that 39 women (45.9%) had between one and two pregnancies, 22 (25.9%) had three to four pregnancies, and 24 (28.2%) reported five or more pregnancies. Regarding pregnancy outcomes, 20 respondents (23.5%) had a history of miscarriage, while 9 (9.1%) had experienced a stillbirth. At the time of the survey, 12 women (12.1%) were currently pregnant.

A large majority of respondents, 89 (89.9%), reported attending antenatal care (ANC) during their last pregnancy. ANC attendance by trimester was distributed as follows: 12 women (12.1%) attended in the

first trimester, 30 (30.3%) in the second trimester, and 47 (47.5%) in the third trimester. Ten respondents (10.1%) did not attend ANC. Place of delivery during the last pregnancy varied, with 57 women (57.6%) delivering at a health facility, 6 (6.1%) delivering at home, and 36 (36.4%) utilizing traditional birth attendants.

Table 3: Pregnancy Experiences Among Women of Reproductive Age Pre-Intervention Survey, Ekiti State, Nigeria (N=99)

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percent (%)	Mean (SD)
Age (years)	—	—	—	28.6 (±5.4)
Ever been pregnant?	Yes	85	85.9	
	No	14	14.1	
Number of pregnancies (among ever pregnant)	1-2 pregnancies	39	45.9*	3.1 (±1.6)
	3-4 pregnancies	22	25.9	
	5 or more pregnancies	24	28.2	
History of miscarriage	Yes	20	23.5	
	No	65	76.5	
History of stillbirth	Yes	9	9.1	
	No	90	90.9	
Currently pregnant	Yes	12	12.1	
	No	87	87.9	
Attended antenatal care (ANC) in last pregnancy	Yes	89	89.9	
	No	10	10.1	
ANC attendance by trimester	1st trimester	12	12.1	
	2nd trimester	30	30.3	
	3rd trimester	47	47.5	
	Did not attend ANC	10	10.1	
Place of birth in last pregnancy	Health facility	57	57.6	
	Home	6	6.1	
	Traditional birth attendant	36	36.4	

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2025

This pre-intervention survey shines a spotlight on the realities of contraceptive use and pregnancy experiences among women of reproductive age in Ekiti State. Despite the well-documented benefits of family planning in reducing unintended pregnancies and improving maternal health (Abah et al., 2024; Abubakar, 2024), only about **36.4%** of women reported using contraceptives prior to the intervention. This echoes a troubling trend seen across Nigeria and other low- and middle-income countries where uptake remains stubbornly low (Akinwale et al., 2020; Abubakar & Abubakar, 2024).

Interestingly, among those using contraception, the overwhelming majority favored pills—accounting for 91.4% of users—highlighting a clear preference for this method. This preference is not surprising and aligns well with earlier studies by Gbenga-Epebinu et al. (2020) and Abdulrazaq et al. (2014), who

suggest that ease of access and familiarity keep pills in the spotlight, even as other effective options like IUCDs and implants remain underutilized.

The profile of the respondents—with most aged 30 to 39 years and married—matches previous findings that these women are more likely to embrace contraception due to their reproductive goals and family dynamics (Durowade et al., 2017; Abah et al., 2024). Yet, despite a strong showing of tertiary education (41.4%), contraceptive use is far from universal. This gap underlines a critical insight: knowledge alone isn't enough. Deep-seated cultural and religious beliefs continue to shape attitudes and behaviors around contraception, creating barriers that education alone can't dismantle (Akamike et al., 2020; Agunbiade & Osezua, 2018).

Pregnancy experiences further reveal a story of high fertility—averaging 3.1 pregnancies per woman, with over a quarter experiencing five or more pregnancies. This suggests a lingering unmet need for family planning and echoes the findings of Durowade et al. (2017). The notable rates of miscarriage (23.5%) and stillbirth (9.1%) remind us of the urgent maternal health challenges faced by many women, reinforcing calls for improved healthcare services (Ameyaw et al., 2021).

On a positive note, most women (89.9%) attended antenatal care during their last pregnancy—a critical step for safeguarding maternal and newborn health. However, with just 12.1% starting ANC in the first trimester, opportunities for early intervention are being missed (Gbenga-Epebinu et al., 2020). The data on delivery locations tell a compelling story too: while 57.6% delivered in health facilities, a significant 42.4% still gave birth at home or with traditional birth attendants. This pattern underscores the ongoing challenges of healthcare access and cultural preferences, especially in rural and semi-urban areas (Adebowale et al., 2021; Durowade et al., 2017).

Applying the Health Belief Model, these findings reveal that while women may be aware of contraceptive benefits and risks, perceived barriers such as cultural opposition and limited access significantly curb uptake (Katatsky, 1977; Montano & Kasprzyk, 2002). This paints a clear path forward: reproductive health programs must be deeply community-rooted, culturally sensitive, and designed to empower women by addressing myths, fears, and structural barriers (Kumar et al., 2024; Akamike et al., 2019). In essence, this baseline survey isn't just a snapshot; it's a call to action.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the baseline data underscore the multifaceted influences on contraceptive utilization and pregnancy outcomes in Ekiti State, highlighting critical areas for targeted interventions to enhance reproductive health and reduce maternal and child morbidity and mortality.

REFERENCES

- Abah, M. G., Ocheche, U. S., Abah, I., Etuk, M. S., & Markson, E. J. (2024). Contraceptive methods continuation and its determinants among acceptors on repeat visits to a Nigerian university teaching hospital: A 10-year review. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 11(5), 1791–1795. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20241169>
- Abdulrazaq, A. G., Kabir, S., Mohammad, N. S., & Suleiman, I. H. (2014). The effect of educational intervention on family planning knowledge, attitudes, and practices among married women in a military barrack in northern Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 18(1), 93–101.
- Abubakar, I. B. (2024). Nigerian women's modern contraceptive use: Evidence from NDHS 2018. *Reproduction and Fertility*, 5(2), e230089. <https://doi.org/10.1530/RAF-23-0089>
- Adebowale, S. A., Fagbamigbe, F. A., & Bamgboye, E. A. (2021). Contraceptive use: Implication for completed fertility, parity, progression and maternal nutritional status in Nigeria. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 15(4), 60–67.
- Akamike, I. C., Okedo-Alex, I. N., Eze, I. I., Ezeanosike, O. B., & Uneke, C. J. (2020). Why does uptake of family planning services remain sub-optimal among Nigerian women? A systematic review of challenges and implications for policy. *Contraception and Reproductive Medicine*, 5(30). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40834-020-00131-0>

- Akamike, I. C., Okedo-Alex, I. N., Madubueze, U. C., & Umeokonkwo, C. D. (2019). Does community mobilisation improve awareness, approval and uptake of family planning methods among women of reproductive age in Ebonyi State? Experience from a quasi-experimental study. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 33(17). <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2019.33.17.17401>
- Akinwale, D., Okafor, A., Akinbade, O., & Ojo, C. (2020). Determinants of modern contraceptives utilization among women of reproductive age in rural community, Osun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*, 13(2), 1173.
- Akinyemi, A., Adedini, S., Hounton, S., Akinlo, A., Adedeji, O., Adonri, O., Friedman, H., Shiferaw, S., Maïga, A., Amouzou, A., & Barros, A. (2015). Contraceptive use and distribution of high-risk births in Nigeria: A sub-national analysis. *Global Health Action*, 8, 29745. <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v8.29745>
- Durowade, K. A., Omokanye, L. O., Elegbede, O. E., Adetokunbo, S., Olomofe, C. O., Ajiboye, A. D., & Sanni, T. A. (2017). Barriers to contraceptive uptake among women of reproductive age in a semi-urban community of Ekiti State, Southwest Nigeria. *Ethiopian Journal of Health Sciences*, 27(2), 121–128.
- Gbenga-Epebinu, M., Okafor, N., & Olofinbiyi, R. (2020). Utilization of modern contraceptives among couples in Ilokun community in Ado Local Government Area, Ekiti State. *Euro Afro Studies International Journal*, 1(3), 1–13.
- Ibikunle, O. O., Ipinimo, T. M., Afape, A. O., Ibikunle, A. I., Bakare, C. A., Ajidagba, B., Ibirongbe, D. O., Ajidahun, E. O., Durowade, K. A., Akinwumi, A. F., Faniku, A., & Adelekan, B. (2023). Trends and determinants of non-utilization of modern contraception in Ekiti State, Nigeria: A ten-year review. *Journal of Mother and Child*, 27(1), 42–51. <https://doi.org/10.34763/jmotherandchild.20232701.d-22-00067>
- Kumar, R., Anwar, M., Naeem, N., Asim, M., Kumari, R., & Pongpanich, S. (2024). Effect of health education on knowledge, perception, and intended contraceptive use for family planning among university students in Pakistan. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 28474. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-79550-5>
- Montano, D., & Kasprzyk, D. (2002). Theory of reasoned action, theory of planned behavior and the integrated behavioral model. In K. Glanz, B. K. Rimer, & F. M. Lewis (Eds.), *Health behavior and health education: Theory, research, and practice* (3rd ed., pp. 67–96). Jossey-Bass.
- Solanke, B., Oyediran, K., & Adebayo, S. (2021). Contraceptives use in Ekiti State: Determinants and socio-ecological factors. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, 25(2), 58–67.
- World Health Organization. (2018). Family planning/contraception. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/family-planning-contraception>